

INTELLECTUAL GAMES AS A FORMATION FACTOR IN STUDENTS INTEREST IN HISTORY IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION AT SCHOOL

Faniya Avzalovna Akhmedshina

Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990730>

Abstract. *In the conditions of the modern dynamically developing world, the current education system, along with the improvement of the forms and methods that have justified themselves in the practice of educational activities, form a student who is able to independently obtain information and use it competently, is faced with the task of finding new forms of enhancing the cognitive activity of schoolchildren. In this, of course, along with various pedagogical technologies, intellectual games play an important role, which will make the process of acquiring knowledge by the student more diverse and interesting. Intellectual games make it possible to turn a lesson not only into an environment for acquiring knowledge, but also create favorable conditions for the socialization of the student, unlocking his potential through self-realization in the game, and provide motivation for a better continuation of learning. In the process of intellectual games, research activities, students form important components of creative activity to find a solution to the problem. The article deals with the problem of using gaming technologies in history lessons in high school. The given examples of games were tested in the course of practical activities in several schools in the city of Jizzakh.*

Keywords: *student's cognitive activity, motivation, intellectual games, creative activity, educational material, student's independence, creative potential.*

Introduction. The urgency of the problem.

In the conditions of the modern dynamically developing world, new tasks have arisen for the current education system: 1. improving the forms and methods of educational activities that have justified themselves in practice to form the student's skills and desires to independently obtain the educational information he needs and use it; 2. the need for an active search for new forms of activation of his cognitive activity in this direction.

To successfully solve these problems, new approaches to information and scientific and methodological support of the educational process, new pedagogical technologies, the formation and development of student motivation for educational and cognitive activity, and interest in the subject are required. The environment of new forms and teaching methods that meet these requirements is played by game learning technologies, including intellectual games in the subjects being taught. The intellectual game is an interesting and fruitful form of active participation in the lesson of each student, increasing the value of knowledge in the subject. The developing activity of students makes it possible to activate the cognitive activity of students in the subject, increase the level of erudition, stimulate their creative activity, form independence, initiative, develop abilities and creative opportunities. Because it opens up a new scope for personal creativity, gaining experience in interpersonal relationships, developing the cognitive and communicative activity of schoolchildren, creates an opportunity for each student to show acquired general educational skills and abilities, to show intellectual abilities, creativity.

Long-term experience of world pedagogy has long proved that students memorize better and develop useful skills necessary in life and study when it is presented in a playful way. As the prominent Czech writer and teacher Jan Amos Komensky (1592-1670) emphasized in his writings: "Children are always willing to do something. This is very useful, and therefore not only should this not be interfered with, but measures must be taken to ensure that they always have something to do.

The use of gaming techniques for presenting material significantly increases the attention and interest of students in the material being studied. In this case, the game in the form of children's independence to the greatest extent affects the mental development of the child.

According to B.R. Mandel, the author of books and articles on mind games in general, and on school subjects in particular: "the use of mind games in educational practice, and today there is no doubt that the mind game as a socio-cultural phenomenon is one of the most powerful means that form and improve not only intellectual development, but also communication skills, social, socio-psychological, personal and professional qualities of a person. "... unpredictability makes the intellectual game a very specific form of cognitive creative activity." Intellectual games combine the features of gaming and educational activities, they "develop theoretical thinking, requiring the formulation of concepts, the performance of basic mental operations (classification, analysis, synthesis, etc.). On the other hand, this activity is a means of achieving a game result (winning a competition), an unprecedented process of constant development of participants in an intellectual game in the course of solving a chain of problem situations [4].

Presentation of the main material of the study.

Modern scientific teachers attach great importance to the use of intellectual games in educational practice. Researchers analyzing the educational process at school rightly note that the share of entertainment is extremely small in educational work - only 4% of other teaching methods and techniques. Although the quality of mastering the subject depends on the degree of interest in the subject, on learning with enthusiasm. Mass practice reacted to the aggravation of the problem with the so-called non-standard lessons, whose main goal is to excite and retain students' interest in educational work[3]. The importance of properly selected and well-organized intellectual games in the comprehensive development of schoolchildren, awakening their interest in the subjects studied, better assimilation and consolidation of acquired knowledge is increasing.

This also applies to the subject of history, the most saturated information. The new State educational standards of general and secondary education in Uzbekistan aim to familiarize students with the history and culture of the peoples of the world and their country, create conditions for mastering and awakening interest in a certain system of historical knowledge, the ability to navigate historical information, evaluate historical events, improve the overall competencies in fundamental and historical sciences [6].

The relevance of interest in intellectual games is currently increasing due to the oversaturation of the modern student with information. Well-prepared and carried out intellectual game gives pleasure from contacts with game partners; the excitement of waiting for unforeseen situations and their resolution during the game; the pleasure of demonstrating your capabilities to partners; the need to make decisions in complex and often uncertain, and sometimes simply unforeseen conditions and situations; fairly quick clarification of the consequences of decisions (answers); pleasure from the successes of the intermediate and final [8].

Intellectual-cognitive game tasks on the subject being studied are liked by schoolchildren of any age. Because an intellectual game as a form of a lesson creates a situation of psychological looseness, live communication, serves as a kind of practice for using the knowledge gained in the lesson and outside of class time. Such lessons and extra-curricular activities are necessary for the education of a creative, active personality, as they stimulate the intellectual growth of the individual, contribute to the improvement of the cultural level of schoolchildren. This activity is especially useful for schoolchildren who are fond of intellectual games. The organization of an intellectual game in practice, of course, requires the teacher to take a creative approach to the methodological part and organize the lesson itself or extracurricular activities, the formation of interest and motivation for this form of learning among their students. This raises the question: how to make the history lesson more interesting, useful and memorable for students?

This topic is very relevant, as society requires activity and a high level of knowledge from students, a painless entry into the process of social relations. Intellectual games that contribute to intellectual development, revealing the individual potential of the student, help at the same time work in a team, since games are mostly team games. As the practice of using intellectual games has shown, they positively influence the development of a sense of duty and responsibility, the desire for mutual assistance, solidarity, the habit of subordinating personal interests to the interests of the team.

The practical experience of talented teachers around the world has shown that learning based on an active approach, based on solving creative problems, can actively develop the creative potential of students and act as a strong motivation for learning. Intellectual-cognitive games, quizzes, game tasks have a positive impact on the intellectual growth of the individual, contribute to the improvement of schoolchildren's knowledge. A variety of content and forms of mastering educational material significantly increases the efficiency and effectiveness of the educational process.

The use of intellectual games contributes to the development of cognitive interests, thought processes and positive motivation for schoolchildren's learning. Intellectual games involve all students in the learning and gaming process, and contribute to the formation of a more conscious interest in obtaining new knowledge. "Carried away by a lively, emotional game, children more easily learn and acquire various skills, abilities and knowledge that they will need in life" [2].

At present, interest in the game around the world, especially in the intellectual game, is growing rapidly. Such forms of intellectual games appear and develop that cover entire regions or even countries, even acquiring an international character, which naturally leads to an increase in interest in them, an increase in both the number of games and their diversity.

In December 2018, a series of intellectual games was held in Tashkent for the first time, held by employees of the Penza State Technological University (Russia), dedicated to the achievements of Russian scientists in the field of natural sciences. In total, more than 70 people took part in the intellectual games. Smart School teachers noted that schoolchildren were interested in the games and expressed their desire to continue cooperation in the future [5].

The first International Intellectual Games (MII) were held from July 8 to 15, 2018, and the second from June 30 to July 10, 2022 in Yakutia (Russia). The International Mind Games have become a unique event in the world, a unique platform for the exchange of ideas, for the establishment of personal connections for the future intellectual elite of the world. The language environment of the games for schoolchildren and experts was chosen as the international language

of scientific communication - English. The patronage of the International Mind Games was UNESCO. About 40 countries and 18 regions of Russia (15,000 participants in total) took part in the first International Intellectual Game, and more than 670 students from 17 countries and 16 regions of Russia took part in the second one [1].

Intellectual games are turning into one of the favorite forms of leisure organization in our country. Particularly great importance is attached to the development of intellectual games on a systematic basis among secondary schools, Presidential educational institutions, institutions of secondary specialized and vocational education and higher educational institutions, as well as amateur teams in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 20, 2022 "On measures to transform intellectual "Zakovat" games in the mass educational movement among the population and the development of other intellectual games" [7].

The resolution notes that the winners of the Republican stage of the Zakovat intellectual game among schoolchildren will receive a Zakovat scholarship during the year and will be able to enter higher educational institutions on a paid contract basis without exams [9].

Researchers analyzing the educational process at school rightly note that the share of entertainment is extremely small in educational work - only 4% of other teaching methods and techniques. Although the quality of mastering the subject depends on the degree of interest in the subject, on learning with enthusiasm. Mass practice reacted to the aggravation of the problem with the so-called non-standard lessons, the main goal of which is to excite and retain students' interest in educational work [3].

Intellectual games make it possible to make the process of acquiring knowledge by a student more diverse and exciting, interesting, create special favorable conditions for changing activities, introducing an element of student competition, socializing the student, unlocking his potential through self-realization in the game, and provide motivation for a better continuation of learning.

Our many years of experience in conducting intellectual games in different schools of the city of Jizzakh in the school history course from the 5th to

The 11th grade during 2015-2023 shows the importance of systematic activities aimed at the qualitative and productive perception of educational material, increasing the student's independence, revealing his creative potential. Intellectual games in history allow you to combine the gaming, educational and work activities of the student and teacher for better mastering the subject. Games contribute to the ability to communicate, take into account the opinions of others on the team when solving collective problems, and joint emotional experiences during the game or a situation of success create a favorable emotional background for strengthening interpersonal relationships, activating the process of self-education of the child.

The organization of educational and cognitive activity of students through intellectual games should be systematic in their use, the purposefulness of the game program on all topics of the textbook. Games should evoke and form the need to learn, develop a sustainable cognitive interest in the subject, contribute to the students' solid assimilation of educational material and additional knowledge, as well as the practical application of knowledge and skills acquired in the lesson. At the same time, attention should be paid to the fact that intellectual games are for participants interesting, exciting, meaningful and arouse the desire to participate in it. The topics of the games, questions and tasks should correspond to the level of knowledge obtained within the

framework of the school curriculum. Difficult and unknown questions for students can push them away from active participation in the game.

In this, the compilation of assignment questions for each topic of the textbook plays an important role, which gives a double result. Firstly, the student will study the topic more carefully from the textbook, terms, illustrations and chronology, and secondly, he will feel confident and comfortable during the competition.

Games help the teacher to perform large educational, educational tasks, to exercise constant and targeted control over the assimilation of current educational and additional material, necessary to increase cognitive activity, deepen students' knowledge of the subject being studied.

For example, when passing the topic "Early stages of development of the most ancient person" in the 6th grade, you can compose questions from the textbook in such a way that it is both understandable and interesting and easy. We offer approximate questions on this topic for an intellectual game:

I ROUND "QUESTION-ANSWER"

1. Where were the skeletons of the most ancient person found?

In East Africa

2. What is the age of the "handy man"?

Over 2 million years

3. Where is the Kapova Cave located?

In Bashkiria (Russia)

4. Where is Teshiktash cave located?

In Baysun district (Surkhandarya region)

II ROUND "HISTORY IN PICTURES"

The question is asked: "What type of person is shown in the photo?" An image appears on the monitor screen, according to which the participants of the game must find the correct answer within one minute. And so it continues in all classes using the technology of intellectual games.

What does this lead to?. According to our observations, such questions contribute to the fact that students do not just look at pictures in a textbook on the topic, but try to understand and remember the depicted process or a portrait of a historical figure, a scientist who was the first to discover and write about his discovery. There is a more conscious approach to the illustrations in the textbook.

III ROUND "HISTORICAL TERMS"

1. Ancient people believed that any objects could bring good luck or ward off misfortune.

What was the name of this belief?

Fetishism

2. Belief in the existence of a close connection between the tribal community and some animal, less often a plant or natural phenomenon, has received the name in science

Totemism.

3. Belief in the presence of supernatural beings (spirits, souls) in the world surrounding a person, received the name in science

Animism.

4. What period does the Great Ice Age cover?

The end of the Early Paleolithic and the beginning of the Mesolithic.

Such questions help in a playful way to fix in memory very important for understanding and remembering the ideas of primitive people about the living and inanimate nature around them, their beliefs.

The game helps to fix in memory the most important dates and events of the historical past for a long time. So, for example, when compiling questions on the topic "Tribal Society", we took into account this important factor.

I ROUND "QUESTION-ANSWER"

1. What is the date of the Late Paleolithic era?

40-12 millennium BC uh

2. What are the Mesolithic settlements in Central Asia?

Obishir, Kushilish, Machai

3. What is the main achievement of the Neolithic era?

The transition from an appropriating economy to a producing economy.

4. In what era did people switch to a settled way of life?

During the Neolithic

II ROUND "HISTORY IN PICTURES"

What is shown in the photo?

Neolithic dwellings.

A very interesting part of the game is a group of questions that require the restoration of gaps in the sentence. For example, in the third round, questions can be arranged in such a way that it is better to remember the terms.

III ROUND "HISTORICAL TERMS"

1. A group of relatives who lived and worked together had common tools and weapons....
Genus.

2. The appropriating economy is ...

Gathering, hunting, fishing.

3.... is this an era that is translated from ancient Greek as "new"?
Neolithic.

4. In the Neolithic era, dishes were made from baked clay ...

Ceramics.

TOPIC: ENEOLITHIC AND BRONZE AGE CULTURE

I ROUND "QUESTION-ANSWER"

1. Since what millennium did the early cities of the state appear in the Ancient East?

From the 4th millennium BC. e.

2. In what era did multi-room houses appear?

In the era of the Eneolithic.

3. In which settlement of the Bronze Age do the first signs of city planning appear?

In the settlement of Dzharkutan.

4. What are the most important inventions of the Bronze Age?

Potter's wheel and wheel.

II ROUND "HISTORY IN PICTURES"

What is shown in the photo?

Pottery.

III ROUND "HISTORICAL TERMS"

1. Zamanbaba is
Bronze Age settlement.
2. They alloyed copper with tin, lead or zinc and got ...
Bronze.
3. Patriarchal families are...
Recognition of paternal kinship.
4. Residents achieved great success in the development of various crafts, weaving, pottery, jewelry making, construction. Insert missing words.
Age of Bronze.

This format of using intellectual questions-answers with elements of competition can be used at all stages of the lesson, both when checking and consolidating the knowledge of schoolchildren, and when studying new material, as one of the effective methods for enlivening the lesson, developing attention and memory of students. The competitive nature of games stimulates students' interest in completing tasks, increases their desire to independently search and find additional materials on a given topic. The teacher must create conditions and support the student for an independent desire to learn, help him in this. The pleasure received from the game should create a comfortable state in the classroom and increase the desire to study the subject.

Conclusions and prospects for further research.

An analysis of scientific theories, pedagogical, gaming practice shows that intellectual games in educational practice help to increase students' faith in their own competence and optimism in relation to their intellectual capabilities, in mastering the skills of intellectual self-regulation. Today, there is no doubt that the intellectual game as a socio-cultural phenomenon is one of the most powerful means of shaping and improving not only intellectual development, but also communication skills, social, socio-psychological, personal and professional qualities of a person. [4].

The intellectual game is the most important form of involving students in educational work, it is an effective method of education and training, the formation and development of motivation for educational and cognitive activities, interest in the subject, which will undoubtedly lead to an increase in the general educational level, the development of horizons.

Such games can be held regularly between teams. In a team game, a sense of duty and responsibility develops, the desire for mutual assistance, the subordination of personal interests to the interests of the team. The use of intellectual games contributes to the development of cognitive interests, thought processes and positive motivation for learning in schoolchildren.

REFERENCES

1. More than 670 schoolchildren from 17 countries participate in the International Mind Games in Yakutia <https://ysia.ru/bolee-670-shkolnikov-iz-17-stran-uchastvuyut-v-mezhdunarodnyh-intellektualnyh-igrah-v-yakutii/>
2. The influence of intellectual games on the development of cognitive abilities in younger students. "Game as a means of developing the individual abilities of the child."
3. Intellectual and educational games for schoolchildren <https://ped-kopilka.ru/igry-konkursy-razvlechenija/intelektualnye-igry-dlja-detei-shkolnogo-vozrasta/intelektualnye-igry-dlja-shkolnikov.html>

4. Intellectual and educational games for schoolchildren <https://ped-kopilka.ru/igry-konkursy-razvlechenija/intelektualnye-igry-dlja-detei-shkolnogo-vozrasta/intelektualnye-igry-dlja-shkolnikov.html>
5. Mandel B.R. Intellectual game: a socio-cultural phenomenon in motion (to questions of history and definition of essence) // Modern problems of science and education. - 2009. - No. 2.
6. URL: <https://science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=1079> (date of access: 05/24/2023).
7. The first intellectual games for schoolchildren in Tashkent went with a bang <https://uz.sputniknews.ru/20181203/Eto-ucება-i-igra-intellektualnye-igry-dlya-detej-v-Tashkente-proshli-na-ura-10152062.html>
8. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 6
9. April 2017 No. 187 “On State Educational Standards for General and Secondary Education” // <http://lex.uz/docs/3153714>
10. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 20, 2022 PP-96 "On measures to turn the intellectual game "Zakovat" into a mass educational movement among the population and the development of other intellectual games" <https://lex.uz/docs/5834316>
11. Historical aspects of the definition of socio-cultural phenomenon of the game
12. Started the final of the intellectual game "Zakovat" among schoolchildren <https://uz.sputniknews.ru/20221009/startoval-final-intellektualnoy-igry-zakovat-sredi-shkolnikov-28960408.html>
13. Jan Amos Comenius: 17 rules of education. - Access mode: <http://www.pravmir.ru/yan-amos-komenskij-18-pravil-uspeshnogo-vospitaniya/>